

Google Scholar

Crossref doi

scopus

Impact factor 6.2

Geoscience Journal

ISSN:1000-8527

Indexing:

- » Scopus
- » Google Scholar
- » DOI, Zenodo
- » Open Access

 www.geoscience.ac

Registered

RISK AWARENESS AND SAFETY PRACTICES AMONG CONSTRUCTION WORKERS: EVIDENCE FROM PARADIP CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY

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ABSTRACT

Construction work is one of the most hazardous occupations globally. Construction workers are at risk of falls, electrocution, chemical exposure, and machinery-related injuries. Despite established safety regulations and guidelines, accidents in the construction sector occur frequently. Inadequate knowledge, negative attitudes, and unsafe practices are recognised as key contributors to these accidents. Identifying the gaps between workers' knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding safety measures and bridging them is therefore essential for improving workplace safety performance.

The current study aimed to assess the knowledge, attitudes, and practices related to safety measures among construction workers in the selected construction industry in Paradip. Therefore, A cross-sectional survey was employed. Data were collected using a structured self-administered questionnaire covering demographic characteristics, safety knowledge, attitudes toward safety measures, and workplace safety practices. Participants were selected through convenience sampling based on the inclusion criteria.

The results revealed, most workers had a moderate knowledge of safety practice (56%; mean 12.98 ± 3.58), a large number demonstrated a neutral attitude towards safety measures (66%; mean 41.02 ± 5.14), and the majority had moderate safety practices (53%; mean 22.94 ± 8.64). Knowledge had a weak positive correlation with attitude ($r = 0.27$) and practice ($r = 0.11$); while attitude had a moderate negative correlation with practice ($r = -0.36$), suggesting that knowledge alone cannot ensure safe practice. Enforcing training programs periodically, mentoring workplace safety practices, are necessary to improve consistent safety practices among construction workers.

KEYWORDS: Risk, awareness, safety, practices, construction, workers, evidence, Paradip, industry

1. INTRODUCTION

Construction industry is a major contributor to infrastructure development and economic growth worldwide; and it is widely recognized as one of the most hazardous occupational sectors globally. Construction workers are estimated to face a significantly higher risk of fatal injury as compared to those in other industries. As per the International Labour Organization (ILO),[1] the construction sector accounts a disproportionately high occupational fatalities, with approximately 108,000 construction workers dying each year worldwide due to work related accidents. These statistics underscore the urgent need for safety management strategies in construction sectors.

Construction projects often involve complex engineering process, rapidly changing work environments, and multiple simultaneous tasks, all of which significantly increase the risk for workplace hazards such as, working at heights, heavy machinery operation, electrical installations, handling of material, excavation, and exposure to hazardous substances. Majority

of accidents are related to falls, electrocution, and equipment-associated injuries. International occupation safety regulations and engineering standards have therefore been established to minimize workplace hazards and promote safer practices.

Organization for Occupational Safety and International Labour Organization provide comprehensive safety guidelines for construction works, related to fall protection, scaffolding safety, use of personal protective equipment, and hazard communication. Moreover, modern construction projects significantly implement Safety Management Systems (SMS) integrated systematic procedures like hazard identification, risk assessment, safety training, incident reporting, and safety supervision.

Even if the established safety regulations and management systems available, accidents continue to occur frequently in construction industries. One of the major challenges in implementing safety regulations is the gap between workers' knowledge and behavior. Previous studies indicate, inadequate knowledge of safety measures, indifferent attitudes toward safety compliance, and unsafe workplace practices significantly associated with accidents in construction sites. Exploring and understanding workers' level of knowledge, attitudes, and practices is therefore essential to identify barriers in order to implement safety measures effectively.

Although several studies available on construction safety management and accident prevention strategies, very few studies have focused on evaluating the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of construction workers regarding safety measures in specific industrial settings. Assessing these factors help to identify training needs, determine strategies for safety awareness improvement, and strengthening the implementation of engineering safety management systems.

Therefore, the current study aimed to assess the knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding the safety measures among construction workers in selected construction sites at Paradip. the study found that knowledge and attitude alone are insufficient to ensure safe practices unless supported by organizational commitment, continuous training, effective supervision, and availability of safety resources. The findings of this study are expected to provide evidence for improving safety training programs, strengthening safety supervision, and enhancing the effectiveness of safety management systems in construction environments.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Research Approach: A **quantitative research approach** was adopted to assess the knowledge, attitudes, and practices objectively, related to occupational safety practices among construction workers.

2.2 Research Design: The study followed a cross-sectional survey research design. This allows the systematic assessment of knowledge, attitudes, and safety practices of construction workers at a single point of time without manipulating the study environment.

2.3 Variables of the Study: The study included the following variables:

- **Independent variables:** safety training
- **Dependent variable:** knowledge regarding safety measures, attitude and practices toward safety implementation by construction workers.
- **Demographic variables:** age, education level, work experience, and other characteristics.

2.4 Study Setting: The study was conducted at a selected construction site in Paradip, Odisha, India, based on accessibility, active construction activities, and the availability of workers during the data collection period.

2.5 Population: The target population are the construction workers.

2.6 Sample: The study sample comprised construction workers employed at the selected construction sites, available during the study period, meeting the inclusion criteria and consented to participate.

2.7 Sample Size: A total of 106 construction workers were included in the study. The sample size was considered adequate for descriptive and correlational analysis.

2.8 Sampling Technique: A convenience sampling technique was used. Construction workers present at the selected construction sites during the data collection period and willing to participate were invited to participate in the study. This non-probability sampling technique was selected due to time limitations, and easy availability of participants at the work sites.

2.9 Eligibility Criteria:

Inclusion Criteria

- Construction workers employed at selected construction sites in Paradip
- Age 20 years and above
- Had at least six months of work experience at the construction site
- Know English, Hindi, or Oriya
- Provided informed consent to participate in the study

Exclusion Criteria

- Administrative personnel and supervisors not directly involved in construction work
- Absent during data collection
- Less than 6 months of employment at the construction site
- Unwilling to participate or did not provide informed consent
- Temporary visitors or subcontractors not regularly employed at the site

2.10 Data Collection Instrument

Data were collected using a **structured self-administered questionnaire** designed to assess the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of construction workers regarding workplace safety measures. The questionnaire consisted of four sections:

- **Section A:** Demographic data (age, education, work experience, etc.)
- **Section B:** Knowledge regarding workplace safety measures
- **Section C:** Attitude towards workplace safety measures
- **Section D:** Self-report of safety practices at the workplace

2.11 Validity and Reliability

The questionnaire was developed based on previously validated instruments used in workplace safety research and modified to suit the construction work context. Content validity was reviewed by the experts in occupational safety and research methodology field. The reliability was established using Cronbach's alpha, indicating acceptable internal consistency of the items of the questionnaire.

2.12 Pilot Study

A pilot study was conducted to evaluate the clarity, and applicability of the study tools. Approximately 10% of the intended sample ($n = 11$) construction workers participated in the pilot study using the same sampling technique and similar study settings. Participants included in the pilot study were excluded from the final study sample. The pilot study showed:

- Questionnaire items were comprehensible
- Average time needed to answer the questionnaire was 20–25 minutes
- Data collection procedure was feasible in the construction site
- Minor language modification made to improve understanding

2.13 Data Collection Procedure

Following administrative permission from the relevant authorities, construction workers were approached, purpose of the study was explained, and written informed consent was obtained prior to participation.

Data collected through the structured self-administered questionnaire. To minimize disruption of work activities, data collected during work breaks and after work shifts. Some responses were collected using printed questionnaires, while others through a Google Forms link shared with participants. Confidentiality and anonymity were maintained throughout the data collection process.

2.14 Ethical Considerations

Administrative permissions were obtained from the relevant authorities. Respondents were informed about the purpose of the study, assured confidentiality of their responses. Participants were also informed that, their participation was voluntary, and they can withdraw from the study at any time.

No physical or psychological harm was associated with the study participants, and all the ethical principles related to the study involving human participants were strictly followed.

2.15 Data Analysis

Collected data were coded and entered into SPSS for analysis and the following statistical methods were used:

- **Descriptive statistics:** frequency, percentage, mean, and SD to summarize demographic characteristics and KAP scores
- **Inferential statistics:** correlation and association tests to examine relationships between knowledge, attitudes, and practices. The level of statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Demographic Characteristics of the Participants

A total 106 construction workers were participated in the study. Most of them were between 30 to 40 years age group (40%), followed by aged 40 to 50 years (32%), indicating the participants were within the economically productive age range. Majority of participants had secondary education (28%), while 25% were graduates and 21% held diploma qualifications, indicating a relatively educated workforce.

As per the occupational roles, engineers constituted the largest group (41%), followed by skilled workers (23%) and unskilled labourers (17%). Majority of workers had more than five

years of experience in the construction industry (64%), and nearly half had been employed at their current workplace for more than one year.

A high proportion of workers (91%) had received prior safety training, and 51% reported experiencing at least one workplace injury during their career. The workforce also included a slightly higher proportion of migrant workers (52%) compared with local workers (48%).

These findings underscore the participation of an experienced workforce with prior safety training exposure, yet with substantial injury experience, indicating possible gaps between knowledge and practice.

3.2 Level of Knowledge of Construction workers regarding Workplace Safety Measures

Table 1. presents the level of knowledge of construction workers regarding safety measures. Knowledge scores were categorized as poor, moderate, and good. The mean knowledge score was 12.98 ± 3.58 on a scale of 0–20, indicating a generally moderate level of knowledge among construction workers. The study found 56% of construction workers with a moderate level of knowledge, while 38% with good knowledge, and 6% showed poor knowledge regarding workplace safety, suggests that safety information may not be adequately comprehensive or consistently reinforced.

3.3 Attitude toward Safety Measures

Table 2. depicts, the mean attitude score toward workplace safety was 41.02 ± 5.14 on a scale of 10–50, indicating an overall favourable attitude towards safety practices; on the other hand, 66% of workers had a neutral attitude, while 23% had an unfavourable attitude and only 11% showed a clearly favourable safety attitude, indicates that though workers may recognize the importance of safety, but they are indifferent attitude wise. Neutral attitudes may reflect weak motivation, poor safety culture, or inadequate managerial reinforcement of safety behavior at construction sites.

3.4 Safety Practices among Construction Workers

Table 3. reports the mean safety practice score was 22.94 ± 8.64 on a scale with possible range between 13 to 65, reflecting moderate implementation of safety practices. More than half of the workers (53%) exhibited moderate safety practices, while 30% showed poor practices and only 17% demonstrated good practices. In spite of moderate knowledge and generally acceptable attitudes, the level of safety practice remained suboptimal, indicates some knowledge–practice gap, reflects that the workers may understand safety guidelines but fail to consistently follow them may be due to factors like time pressure, inadequate supervision, lack of enforcement, or insufficient safety resources. The safety practice observed in this study aligns with study conducted by Danimoh et al. (2023) [2] and Mohd Azhari et al. (2023) [3].

3.5 Association between KAP and Demographic Variables

There are several significant associations found between knowledge, attitude, practice (KAP), and demographic variables.

Table 4. presents the association between knowledge scores and socio-demographic variables among construction workers ($n = 106$). The association was examined using the chi-square test and the result found that current job role had a statistically significant association with knowledge scores ($p = < 0.001$), indicating that knowledge levels varied significantly according to the nature of the job performed. Higher knowledge observed among skilled workers, engineers, and supervisors. Similarly, living arrangements found to have a significant

association with knowledge scores ($p = 0.02$), suggesting differences in knowledge levels based on whether participants lived alone, with family, or with co-workers.

A borderline significant association observed between knowledge scores and duration of employment at the current workplace ($p = 0.05$), total work experience in the construction industry ($p = 0.05$), and receipt of prior safety training ($p = 0.05$), indicating longer work exposure and prior safety training associated with better knowledge levels.

There was no statistically significant association found between knowledge scores and other demographic variables such as age ($p = 0.48$), highest level of education ($p = 0.09$), marital status ($p = 0.07$), experience of workplace injury ($p = 0.15$), type of work performed ($p = 0.60$), employment type ($p = 0.26$), place of residence ($p = 0.51$), monthly income ($p = 0.36$), addiction status ($p = 0.35$), and presence of chronic health conditions ($p = 0.99$); indicates these variables did not significantly influence the knowledge scores of the participants.

Table 5. depicts the association between attitude scores and selected socio-demographic variables among construction workers ($n = 106$), analyzed using the chi-square test revealed that highest level of education demonstrated a statistically significant association with attitude scores ($p = < 0.001$), indicating that participants with higher educational attainment had more positive attitudes towards safety practices. A significant association was also observed between current job role and attitude scores ($p = 0.03$), suggesting variation in attitude existed across different occupational roles. Similarly, total work experience in the construction industry was significantly associated with attitude scores ($p = 0.03$), indicating more experience contributed to more favourable safety attitudes.

Furthermore, prior safety training had a significant association with attitude scores ($p = 0.03$), highlighting the positive influence of formal training on workers' safety attitudes. Experience of workplace injury was also significantly associated with attitude scores ($p = 0.03$), suggesting, workers who had previously experienced injuries demonstrated heightened safety concern. In addition, living arrangements exhibited a statistically significant association with attitude scores ($p = 0.01$). Presence of chronic health conditions was also found to be significantly associated with attitude scores ($p = 0.04$).

Though not reaching statistical significance at the 0.05 level, a borderline association was observed between attitude scores and monthly income range ($p = 0.06$) and addiction status ($p = 0.06$).

There was no statistically significant association found between attitude scores and other demographic variables, such as age ($p = 0.26$), marital status ($p = 0.22$), duration of employment at the current workplace ($p = 0.63$), type of work performed ($p = 0.42$), employment type ($p = 0.57$), and place of residence ($p = 0.37$).

This finding is supported by the study conducted by Srivastav et al. (2022) [4] and Shrestha et al. (2025) [5].

Table 6. presents the association between practice levels and selected socio-demographic variables among construction workers ($n = 106$). The associations were examined using the chi-square test demonstrated that highest level of education was significantly associated with practice levels ($p = < 0.001$), indicating that workers with higher educational attainment

exhibited better safety practices. A statistically significant association was also found between marital status and practice level ($p = 0.01$).

Further, current job role showed a significant association with practice levels ($p = 0.03$). Total work experience in the construction industry was also found to be significantly associated with practice level ($p = < 0.001$), indicating greater experience linked with improved safety practices.

A significant association observed between practice level and receipt of prior safety training ($p = 0.02$), highlighting the positive impact of safety training on the adoption of safe practices. Further, experience of workplace injury demonstrated a highly significant association with practice level ($p = < 0.001$), suggesting that workers who had previously experienced injuries were more likely to follow safety practices.

The type of work performed was significantly associated with practice level ($p = 0.03$), indicating variation in safety practices across various construction activities. Monthly income range also showed a significant association with practice level ($p = 0.02$). Similarly, living arrangements significantly associated with practice level ($p = 0.03$), reflecting the influence of social and living environments on safety behavior. Additionally, the presence of chronic health conditions significantly associated with practice level ($p = < 0.001$).

There was no statistically significant association found between practice level and age ($p = 0.11$), duration of employment at the current workplace ($p = 0.23$), employment type ($p = 0.29$), place of residence ($p = 0.25$), and addiction status ($p = 0.38$).

The above findings have its support from the study conducted by Afework (2024) [6], Geleta (2021) [7], and Sehsah et al. (2020) [8].

3.6 Correlation between Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice

Correlation analysis revealed several relationships between the KAP variables.

Table 7 suggests a weak but statistically significant positive correlation observed between knowledge and attitude ($r = 0.27$, $p = 0.01$), indicating, workers with more knowledge tend to demonstrate more positive safety attitudes.

Table 8 indicates a very weak positive correlation was observed between knowledge and practice ($r = 0.11$), indicating that only knowledge does not necessarily improve safety practice. These findings mirrors the findings of Sharma et al. (2025) [9] and Shingnad et al. (2024) [10].

Table 9 shows a moderate negative correlation observed between attitude and practice ($r = -0.36$, $p = 0.01$), indicates a positive attitude toward safety did not necessarily correspond to better safety practices.

The above findings underscore that knowledge, and attitudes alone are not sufficient to ensure safe practice, and therefore effective safety management systems, supervision, and enforcement mechanisms are mandatory to translate knowledge into practice. The study findings are supported by the study conducted by Aliyi et al. (2024) [11] and Ahmed Abdulla S. (2024) [12].

3.7 Implications of the findings in Construction Safety Management

The findings underscore several practical implications for improving construction site safety.

- Consistent and task-specific safety training programs must be reinforced to make the workers' understand about safety hazards and adopt preventive measures.
- Enforcement of safety measures and close supervision are required to ensure compliance with established safety protocols.
- Organizations must encourage a work culture, where safety is integrated into daily work practices and actively supported by management.
- Engineering safety management systems, including hazard identification, risk assessment, and safety audits, need to be strengthened to minimize workplace risks.

3.8 Future Research Directions

- Explore longitudinal studies to evaluate changes in safety behavior over periods, especially, after the implementation of safety training programs or safety management interventions.
- Examine the impact of organizational safety culture, leadership commitment, and engineering control measures on construction worker safety behavior.
- Study involving larger multi-site samples would provide deeper insights into the factors influencing occupational safety in the construction sector.
- Exploring psychosocial and economic determinants of unsafe behavior
- Developing and validating predictive safety performance models

4. CONCLUSION

The present study assessed the knowledge, attitude, and practice regarding safety measures among construction workers and examined their association with selected socio-demographic variables. The findings revealed that although the majority of construction workers possessed moderate to good knowledge and an overall a favourable attitude towards workplace safety, actual safety practices were moderate.

Significant associations were observed between demographic characteristics like education, job role, work experience, prior safety training, and injury history and safety knowledge, attitude, and practice. The weak correlation between knowledge and practice, along with the negative correlation between attitude and practice, highlights a gap.

Finally, the study concludes that knowledge and attitude alone are insufficient to ensure safe practices unless supported by organizational commitment, continuous training, effective supervision, and availability of safety resources.

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APPENDICES

Table 1: Knowledge of construction workers on safety measures

Level of knowledge	Score range	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Poor	< (Mean – SD) < 9.4	6	6
Moderate	between (Mean – SD) and (Mean + SD) 9.4 – 16.56	60	56
Good	> (Mean + SD) > 16.56	40	38
Total		106	100

Table 2: Attitude of construction workers towards occupational safety

Attitude level	Score range	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Unfavorable	< (Mean – SD) < 35.88	24	23
Neutral	between (Mean – SD) and (Mean + SD) 35.88 – 46.16	70	66
Favorable	> (Mean + SD) > 46.16	12	11
Total		106	100

Table3: Safety practices of construction workers

Practice level	Score range	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Poor	< (Mean – SD) < 14.30	32	30
Moderate	between (Mean – SD) and (Mean + SD) 14.30 – 31.58	56	53
Good	> (Mean + SD) > 31.58	18	17
Total		106	100

Table 4.: Association between Knowledge Scores and Selected Demographic Variables (n = 106)

Socio demographic variables	Total N (%) 106 (100)	Chi square p Value
1. Age (in years)		
20 – 30	26 (24)	0.48
30 – 40	42 (40)	
40 – 50	34 (32)	
50 – 60	04 (4)	
2. Highest level of education		
20 – 30	26 (24)	0.09
30 – 40	42 (40)	
40 – 50	34 (32)	
50 – 60	04 (4)	
3. Marital status		
Single	26 (24)	0.07
Married	78 (74)	
Widowed	02 (2)	
Divorced	00 (00)	
Separated	00 (00)	
4. Current job role		
Unskilled laborer	18 (17)	< 0.001
Skilled worker	24 (23)	
Supervisor	16 (15)	
Engineer	44 (41)	
Manager	04 (4)	

Other	00 (00)	
5. Duration of employment at current workplace		
6–12 months	20 (19)	0.05
>1 year	52 (49)	
>5 years	34 (32)	
6. Total work experience in the construction industry		
<1 year	00 (00)	0.05
1–3 years	14 (13)	
3–5 years	24 (23)	
>5 years	68 (64)	
7. Received any prior safety training		
Yes	96 (91)	0.05
No	10 (9)	
8. Experience of any workplace injury		
Yes	54 (51)	0.15
No	52 (49)	
9. Type of work perform		
Electrical	23 (22)	0.60
Welder	19 (18)	
Grinder	11 (10)	
Fitter	21 (20)	
Scaffolder	15 (14)	
Masonry	17 (16)	
Others	00 (00)	
10. Employment type		
Rate Contract	94 (89)	0.26
Supply worker	12 (11)	
11. Place of residence		
Local (Paradip)	51 (48)	0.51
Migrant	55 (52)	
12. Monthly income range		
Less than ₹20,000	26 (25)	0.36
More than ₹20,000	80 (75)	
13. Living arrangements		
Alone	34 (32)	0.02
With family	46 (43)	
With co- workers	20 (19)	
With friends	06 (6)	
14. Addiction		
Smoking	12 (11)	0.35
Alcohol	16 (15)	
Abstainer	78 (74)	
15. Suffering from any chronic health condition		
Yes	07 (7)	0.99
No	99 (93)	

Table 5.: Association between Attitude Scores and Selected Demographic Variables (n = 106)

Socio demographic variables	Total N (%) 106 (100)	Chi square p Value
1. Age (in years)		
20 – 30	26 (24)	0.26
30 – 40	42 (40)	
40 – 50	34 (32)	
50 – 60	04 (4)	
2. Highest level of education		
20 – 30	26 (24)	< 0.001
30 – 40	42 (40)	
40 – 50	34 (32)	
50 – 60	04 (4)	
3. Marital status		
Single	26 (24)	0.22
Married	78 (74)	
Widowed	02 (2)	
Divorced	00 (00)	
Separated	00 (00)	
4. Current job role		
Unskilled laborer	18 (17)	0.03
Skilled worker	24 (23)	
Supervisor	16 (15)	
Engineer	44 (41)	
Manager	04 (4)	
Other	00 (00)	
5. Duration of employment at current workplace		
6–12 months	20 (19)	0.63
>1 year	52 (49)	
>5 years	34 (32)	
6. Total work experience in the construction industry		
<1 year	00 (00)	0.03
1–3 years	14 (13)	
3–5 years	24 (23)	
>5 years	68 (64)	
7. Received any prior safety training		
Yes	96 (91)	0.03
No	10 (9)	
8. Experience of any workplace injury		
Yes	54 (51)	0.03
No	52 (49)	
9. Type of work perform		
Electrical	23 (22)	0.42
Welder	19 (18)	
Grinder	11 (10)	
Fitter	21 (20)	
Scaffolder	15 (14)	
Masonry	17 (16)	

Others	00 (00)	
10. Employment type		
Rate Contract	94 (89)	0.57
Supply worker	12 (11)	
11. Place of residence		
Local (Paradip)	51 (48)	0.37
Migrant	55 (52)	
12. Monthly income range		
Less than ₹20,000	26 (25)	0.06
More than ₹20,000	80 (75)	
13. Living arrangements		
Alone	34 (32)	0.01
With family	46 (43)	
With co- workers	20 (19)	
With friends	06 (6)	
14. Addiction		
Smoking	12 (11)	0.06
Alcohol	16 (15)	
Abstainer	78 (74)	
15. Suffering from any chronic health condition		
Yes	07 (7)	0.04
No	99 (93)	

Table 6.: Association between Practice Level and Demographic Variables (n = 106)

Socio demographic variables	Total N (%) 106 (100)	Chi square p Value
1. Age (in years)		
20 – 30	26 (24)	0.11
30 – 40	42 (40)	
40 – 50	34 (32)	
50 – 60	04 (4)	
2. Highest level of education		
20 – 30	26 (24)	< 0.001
30 – 40	42 (40)	
40 – 50	34 (32)	
50 – 60	04 (4)	
3. Marital status		
Single	26 (24)	0.01
Married	78 (74)	
Widowed	02 (2)	
Divorced	00 (00)	
Separated	00 (00)	
4. Current job role		
Unskilled laborer	18 (17)	0.03
Skilled worker	24 (23)	
Supervisor	16 (15)	
Engineer	44 (41)	
Manager	04 (4)	

Other	00 (00)	
5. Duration of employment at current workplace		
6–12 months	20 (19)	0.23
>1 year	52 (49)	
>5 years	34 (32)	
6. Total work experience in the construction industry		
<1 year	00 (00)	< 0.001
1–3 years	14 (13)	
3–5 years	24 (23)	
>5 years	68 (64)	
7. Received any prior safety training		
Yes	96 (91)	0.02
No	10 (9)	
8. Experience of any workplace injury		
Yes	54 (51)	< 0.001
No	52 (49)	
9. Type of work perform		
Electrical	23 (22)	0.03
Welder	19 (18)	
Grinder	11 (10)	
Fitter	21 (20)	
Scaffolder	15 (14)	
Masonry	17 (16)	
Others	00 (00)	
10. Employment type		
Rate Contract	94 (89)	0.29
Supply worker	12 (11)	
11. Place of residence		
Local (Paradip)	51 (48)	0.25
Migrant	55 (52)	
12. Monthly income range		
Less than ₹20,000	26 (25)	0.02
More than ₹20,000	80 (75)	
13. Living arrangements		
Alone	34 (32)	0.03
With family	46 (43)	
With co- workers	20 (19)	
With friends	06 (6)	
14. Addiction		
Smoking	12 (11)	0.38
Alcohol	16 (15)	
Abstainer	78 (74)	
15. Suffering from any chronic health condition		
Yes	07 (7)	< 0.001
No	99 (93)	

Table 7.: Correlation between Knowledge and Attitude Scores regarding Safety Measures (n = 106)

Variables	Knowledge	Attitude	Significant at p < 0.05
Knowledge	1	0.27	0.01
Attitude	0.27	1	

Table 8.: Correlation between Knowledge and Practice Scores regarding Safety Measures (n = 106)

Variables	Knowledge	Practice	Significant at p < 0.05
Knowledge	1	0.11	p-value not available
Practice	0.11	1	

Table 9.: Correlation between Attitude and Practice Scores regarding Safety Measures (n = 106)

Variables	Attitude	Practice	Significant at p < 0.05
Attitude	- 0.36	1	0.01
Practice	1	- 0.36	